
**INFORMATION PRODUCTS AND SERVICES MANAGEMENT IN ELECTRONIC
INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT: WITH A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
SELECTED ENGINEERING COLLEGE LIBRARIES IN RTM NAGPUR
UNIVERSITY AREA**

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Abstract :

Technology plays an important role in information management although information management is not about technology. Now days the role of information professionals is beyond issues related to displaying, cataloguing and indexing documents for end users. The library is a growing organism as per Dr. S. R. Ranganathan's fifth law of library science. The growth of collection in terms of quality and quantity, the many subjects of interest to users, increasing costs and limited financial resources force librarians to used data for rational decisions. The present study very specially deals information products and services from the view points of the engineering college libraries. The study has been made meaningful by taking up the studies of with a special reference to selected engineering college libraries in RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur Area.

Introduction:

Engineering education is basic and essential input for national development and for strengthening the industry, economy and ultimately improving the quality of life of the people. The nature of collection in the engineering college libraries are also equally responding to the changing diversion of library in Information Technology environment corresponding, the users behavior in the effective use of the information products which includes print and non print including digital resources are taking a different approach to the information user aspect. Therefore, the libraries need to organize and manage the resources in relation to the information use, behavior and requirement of the users, in this context, the users of the engineering college libraries in RTM Nagpur University area managing electronic information products in engineering college library is challenge to librarian/information manager/ Director of Information resource centre when compared to managing of conventional library, since the environment of the digital libraries in entirely different.

Hence it is essential to know the opinions and levels of awareness of the research clientele or users towards their seeking information and its management and services rendered to them in the engineering college libraries in RTM Nagpur University area. Further, managing information products and preserving them in library are sides of the coin from the user point of college library products concerned.

Objectives of the study:

1. To identify the constraints of the users in the effective use of the products and services.
2. To identify the problem faced by the engineering college librarian in management of information products and services.
3. To determine the extent of use of the various information products and services in the engineering college libraries under study and
4. The main objectives of the study are to survey the user's opinion towards the available information products and services in the engineering college libraries under study.

List of selected Engineering Colleges under study:

The study include only those engineering colleges which are engaged in imparting degree level courses (B.E.) in the field of engineering and Technology.

The colleges under study are:

Sr. No.	Name of College	Establishment Year	Abbreviation
1.	Laxminarayan Institute of Tech., Nagpur	1942	LIT
2.	BapuraojiDeshmukh College of Engineering, Sewagram	1983	BDCE
3.	Manoharbai Patel Inst. Of Engineering & Tech. Gondia.	1983	MPIET
4.	KarmavirDadasahebKannamwar College of Engineering Nagpur	1984	KDK
5.	YeshwantraoChavan College of Engineering, Nagpur	1984	YCCE
6.	Government College of Engineering, Chandrapur	1996	GCE
7.	Anjuman College of Engineering & Tech. Nagpur	1999	ACE
8.	Guru Nanak Institute of Engineering & Tech. Nagpur	2007	GNIE
9.	Data Meghe Institute of Engineering & Tech. Sawangi, Wardha	2008	DMIE
10.	J.D. College of Engineering, Nagpur	2008	JDCE
11.	Rajiv Gandhi College of Engineering & Research	2008	RGCE

Methodology:

To conduct this study, purposive random sampling from Sample engineering college libraries were chosen from RTM Nagpur University Area. A total of 210 respondents chosen through purposive random sampling from the selected sample libraries at the rate of 25-20 from users and 2-4 from the professional staff of each selected libraries.

Data Analysis:**View of users of Electronic information Products:**

It is observed from the table 1 most of the users from traditional, professional engineering college libraries expressed their satisfaction extent to be nil extent with regard to full text data files 2.90 for RGCE and microfilm collection 1.49 IDCE, 1.41 BDCE also video tapes 2.41 in ACE & 2.10 GHIE further it is observed that even though, most of engineering college have electronic information products, the user satisfied is very low with regard to electronic information product except CD-Rom, e-journals, books and full text data base file.

**Table shows Table 1
Users on Information Products in the Libraries.**

Sr No	Statement	LIT	BDCE	MPIET	KDK	YCC	GCE	ACE	GNIE	DMIE	IDCE	RGCE
		WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA
1.	Micro form collection	1.2	1.41	1.21	1.2	1.31	1.41	1.12	1.15	1.21	1.49	1.20
2.	Full text data files	2.45	2.51	2.31	1.51	2.81	2.41	2.65	2.61	2.81	2.91	2.90
3.	Video tapes	1.31	1.40	1.21	1.24	1.44	1.51	2.41	2.10	1.50	1.51	2.00

4.	CD-ROM data base	2.90	2.99	3.41	3.31	3.88	4.00	3.81	3.65	3.81	3.91	3.99
5.	OPAC	3.51	3.88	4.15	3.91	3.87	4.12	3.91	3.65	3.32	3.90	4.10
6.	e-Journals	3.41	3.41	4.11	3.98	3.00	1.12	3.41	2.91	2.00	--	2.10
7.	E-Books	3.8	3.40	3.41	2.10	1.40	1.14	1.20	4.00	2.10	2.1	2.91

WA = Weighted Average N = 220

Purpose of using Information Products:

It is clear from the table 3 that 51.36 percent of respondents use information products for the purpose of their research / study, while 23.18 percent of research uses information products for findings relevant information purpose. 10.00 percent of respondents use these products for career development, however only 7.27. Percent of respondents use information products for other activities such as fun and entertainment and 8.18 percent of respondents use for communication purpose.

Table – 2

Purpose of Using Information Products

Purpose of Approach	Number of Respondents	Percentage
For research / study	113	51.36
For communication	18	8.18
For finding relevant information	51	23.18
Career development	22	10.00
For other activities	16	7.27
Total	220	100

Source of learning to use electronic products:

Table 3 shows that 33.18 percent of respondents acquired skills to use electronic products with their self through. 55.36 percent of respondent acquired skills through guidance from other research scholars, while 17.27 percent respondent are learning through trial and error method, 31.36 percent respondent are learning through external course. But a very few i.e. 7.27 percent respondents acquired skills to use electronic sources through course offered by institutions.

Table – 3

Learning to Electronic Product.

Learning to e-products	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Trial and error	38	17.27
Guidance from other research scholars	124	55.36
Self though	73	33.18
Guidance from library staff	51	23.18
Course offered by institutions	16	7.27
Guidance from lecturers	18	8.18
Guidance from computer staff	22	10.00
External course	69	31.36

Users on Electronic Information Services:

It is observed Table-4 users about the different electronic information services offered in the engineering college offered in the engineering college libraries from the table it is noticed that the users satisfaction towards electronic information services offered by libraries.

Table – 4

Table shows Users on Electronic Information Services provided by engineering college libraries.

Sr. No	Statement	LIT	BDCE	MPIET	KDK	YCC	GCE	ACE	GNE	DMIE	IDCE	RGCE
1.	CAS Services	1.35	1.40	1.7	2.1	2.41	1.15	2.41	2.10	1.7	1.1	1.3
2.	Internet Services	4.1	3.90	4.21	3.51	2.71	3.40	4.1	4.2	3.9	3.71	4.21
3.	Online SDI Services	1.81	1.21	1.1	1.41	2.11	2.21	2.81	1.21	1.41	1.51	1.21
4.	OPAC Services	2.51	2.56	2.71	3.1	2.17	3.41	2.81	2.41	2.57	2.81	2.91
5.	Abstracting Services	2.36	2.45	2.71	3.41	2.1	1.10	1.7	1.91	1.31	1.41	1.71
6.	Online Database services	2.51	2.71	2.90	2.51	3.31	3.41	2.81	2.71	2.81	2.90	3.1
7.	Info net services	2.36	2.51	3.1	3.7	2.91	3.10	2.91	2.7	2.91	2.95	2.71

Further, it is noticed that the users expressed their satisfaction to same positive extent on overall service. The users from traditional and professional engineering college libraries categories expressed their satisfaction to a little extent on electronic information services.

Suggestions:

- ❖ The technology is giving a valuable opportunity for the librarians to create new avenues for the information seekers in the college libraries. There is every need for the librarians to renew their skills periodically and achieve excellence in the library services.
- ❖ User education gains more importance in the present IT environments and emphasis must be laid on this aspect by college authorities' libraries.
- ❖ The top people in the library should become role models to the other staff through their personal usage of technology and their IT knowledge.
- ❖ Who are well trained in their task show more involvement discharging their responsibilities hence; training facilities must be encouraged by the authorities.

Conclusion:

Collection of information products in any engineering college library depends on the users demand. Engineering libraries are playing key role in providing information to users by adopting new techniques through ICT to libraries. In modern electronic era, the user expectations are changing rapidly. However, there is imminent need to diversify the information services in response to the changing needs of the users.

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